

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF TRANSLATED ENGLISH VIDEOS INTO ARABIC ON ENHANCING AL-AZHAR UNIVERSITY (AUG) ENGLISH MAJORS' LISTENING COMPREHENSION SKILLS

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Abstract:

This study investigated the effectiveness of translated English videos into Arabic on enhancing Al-Azhar University-Gaza (AUG) English majors' listening comprehension skills. To achieve the aim of the study, the researchers adopted a quasi-experimental research design which focused on enhancing three main listening skills: getting the main idea, getting details and note taking skills by using translated English videos into Arabic. Twenty female English majors who were enrolled in a listening course during the first semester of the academic year 2016/2017 were the one group sample of the study. They attended the ten classes of the experiment and did a pre and post listening comprehension test. To analyze the data which the tool of the study provided, the researchers used Wilcoxon Test to compare the participants' performance in the listening comprehension pre and posttests and Eta Square to measure the effect size of the study strategy. By the end of the semester, the sample of the study completed a listening comprehension test which consisted of (20) questions focused on getting the main idea, getting details and note taking skills. Results revealed that translated English videos into Arabic have a large effect on enhancing AUG English majors' listening comprehension skills.

Keywords: effectiveness, translated English videos, listening comprehension skills

1. Introduction

Integrated teaching and assessing of language skills are highly appreciated; however, prominent number of applied linguists mentioned their justifications on giving the

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listening skill a specific focus. Listening skill is the most critical skill in language learning as it is the key to speaking and beyond that reading and writing skills. People practice listening much more than other language skills (Dash, 2013, p.1) that is due to the prominent function which listening skill plays in the daily life communication (Drood & Aydinlou, 2016, p.35). In addition, listening plays a vital role in daily live practices and it is used for different purposes such as entertainment, academic purposes or obtaining necessary information. As for foreign language learning, listening is important since it is the first language skill acquired and it is the basic skill for other language skills. In other words, it provides the language input.

No one can deny that listening comprehension is a complex ongoing process which involves the various factors affect students' listening comprehension of oral texts delivered to them (Chen 2013, p.83). Gilakjani & Sabouri (2016, p.127), Woottipong (2014, p.201), Nadjah (2012, p.27) and Graham (2006, p.170-172) agreed that poor grammar, unfamiliar vocabulary, quality of recorded materials, cultural differences, accent misinterpretations about listening tasks, lack of control over the speed at which speakers speak, cannot get things repeated, failure to recognize the signals, previous impact on the students' listening comprehension ability and students' interest and negative attitudes towards listening materials are among the factors that affect students understanding of spoken utterances.

To facilitate the different listening comprehension tasks for EFL learners, several active teaching methods and techniques were presented. Translated English videos into Arabic are among of the recent techniques which are proposed for enhancing listening comprehension skills. Subtitle video is a branch of translation and it is called audiovisual translation in which viewers can read statements of dialogues on the screen as well as watch the images and listen to the dialogues. The captions are typically white upper-case letters against a black background. Subtitle is also defined as the permanently affixed on screen text that represents the narration, dialogue, music, or sound effects (Gorjian, 2014, p.1015). Besides, Gerzymisch-Arbogast (2008, p.113) defined subtitle as "*the written translation of film dialogue appears synchronously with the corresponding dialogues produced on the screen.*" In other words, the translated videos can be changed by the term of subtitle or caption which refers to what the listeners read at the bottom of the screen, or it may refer to the short videos which are spoken in the speakers' language and written in different languages that are easier to understand than the real language of speakers. In this study, the researchers define translated English videos as selected videos chosen from several websites; they may be a movie, a television show or any event. These videos spoken in English language and they are translated into Arabic language; the translation is written at the bottom of the screen.

The use of video during the process of teaching, to visualize what the learners hear which is the first major advantage of using video, is providing samples of real-life situations. Danan (2004, p.67) mentioned that audiovisual material which is enhanced with subtitles is a particularly useful pedagogical tool which can improve the listening comprehension skills of second-language learners. The use of videos with subtitles or

with the use of written languages can facilitate the language learning by helping students to visualize what they hear. Subtitling can also increase language comprehension and leads to additional cognitive benefits. In addition, Zanon (2006, p. 43) showed that the use of subtitled videos encourages strong associations for language use, "*the supplementary effects that both visual images and translation on their own typically entail for foreign language learning, is necessarily very powerful*". Similarly, Baltova (1999, p. 33) pointed the importance of using subtitled films that which provide simultaneous exposure to spoken language, printed text, and visual information to help convey a specific message and may facilitate the content and vocabulary learning. Danan (2004, p.69) added that translated videos can be valuable for comprehension and words' recognition/knowledge. Furthermore, translated videos bridge the gap between reading and listening skills, improve reading, help learners to acquire new vocabulary and idioms with correct pronunciation and follow the plot easily (Zanon, 2006, pp.43-44).

The use of translated videos as a teaching strategy includes three stages in which learners watch a specific video for three times. In the first time students are encouraged to watch the film or part of the film with no subtitles. Then, students are motivated to watch the same film with English subtitles. If the film is not fully understood, students are encouraged to watch the same film with subtitles in local language (Hosogoshi, 2016, p.155). These stages provide foreign language learners with gradual steps to understand the listening material.

There are several translated videos types, and these types are divided according to the language used in the translation. Zanon (2006, p.47) summed up these types as follows: (1) from English dialogues to English subtitles: bimodal subtitling (2) from English dialogues to subtitles in the learner's mother tongue: standard subtitling and (3) from dialogues in the learner's mother tongue to English subtitles: reversed subtitling. Thammineni (2016) said that there are different types of possible combinations between audio and subtitles. The main ones are typically known as standard subtitles (foreign language audio with mother tongue captions), bimodal subtitles (foreign language audio with foreign language subtitles), and reversed subtitles (mother tongue audio with foreign captions). The most commonly used combination is the standard one, the bimodal variety is also commonly used in classroom activities; the use of one or another in class will depend on the goal of the lesson and on the students' level.

Bodies of research papers have been tackled to investigate the effectiveness of different strategies on enhancing the listening comprehension skills of EFL learners. Felicity (2016) examined the type of instructional strategies used by secondary school teachers in the teaching of listening skills in Kiswahili language. Rahimi and Soleymani (2015) investigated the impact of mobile learning on EFL learners' listening anxiety and listening comprehension. Gowhary et al (2015) examined the effect of the video captioning on Iranian EFL learners' listening comprehension in Ilam, Iran (Safir English language institute). Rokni and Ataei (2014) tested the effects of watching English movies with and without subtitles on EFL students' speaking ability. Woottipong (2014) evaluated the listening skills of university students studying English with the use of

video materials and assessed their attitudes towards the use of video materials in teaching listening skills. Damronglaohapan and Stevenson (2013) investigated the effect of short English movies and TV series clips on enhancing English learners' listening skills and their attitude towards such a model.

It is clear that enhancing the oral skills of EFL learners have annoyed researchers around the world. Some investigated the effect of using videos and clips. The viewed studies showed two main related ideas; some studies search for developing listening skills by adopting active teaching strategies while the others focused on using subtitled videos in teaching. Few of these studies explained the relationship between the subtitled videos and the listening ability. None of them tried to explain how the translated English videos correspond on enhancing specific listening skills in which the contribution of audio, video and translation work together to facilitate the content and creates a low anxiety learning environment. Up to the best knowledge of the researchers, none of the researchers in Palestine has investigated the effectiveness of translated English videos on enhancing the listening skills of EFL learners.

The current study focused on revealing how much is useful to connect between what is read in Arabic (the learners' mother tongue) and what is heard to in English (the learning foreign language) to enhance some specific listening comprehension skills: getting the main idea, getting details, and note taking skills.

2. Statement of the Problem

The researchers work at AUG as lectures; they noticed that English majors face difficulties in comprehension of the listening materials in foreign language which affect their performance in other language skills. The current teaching methods for listening courses are still following the traditional way which is based on asking English majors to listen and answer specific questions measuring listening comprehension skills. In other words, there are no visual materials help in comprehension process. As it is noticeable in previous mentioned studies, there were positive impact in using an interesting and enjoyable strategy for teaching listening such as integrating visual and audio materials with translation by viewing the picture with the sound and its translation at the same time and using some videos to close the meaning to the listeners' mind. Consequently, the researchers seek to find out the effectiveness of translated English videos on enhancing English majors' listening skills: getting the main idea, getting details and note taking skills.

3. Material and Methods

To achieve the aims of the study, the researchers adopted the quasi-experimental approach and followed the procedures of a one group experiment. The group of the recent study includes (20) female AUG English majors who were enrolled in a listening course during the first semester of the academic year 2016/2017. Those English majors,

who represent (15%) from the study population, did a pre and post listening comprehension tests.

The researcher prepared a listening comprehension skills test which focuses on measuring the sample level on getting the main idea, getting detailed information, and note taking skills. The same copy of the test was used as a pre and posttest. The test consists of three parts (A, B, C). Part A measures the skill of getting the main idea; it includes five filling gap questions, and the total mark for this question is (20), four marks were given for each question. While part B measures the skill of getting details, it is confined to five multiple choice questions. The total mark for this question is (20) with four marks given for each question. Part C measures the skill of note taking. It consists of a conversation that needed to be completed. The total mark for this question is (20) with two marks given for each question. The total mark of the test was (60). The listening comprehension test was introduced to a jury of specialists in English language and teaching methodology. They recommended identifying the marks for questions and omitting some questions. The items of the test were modified according to their recommendations.

The researchers computed the internal consistency of the questions of the test by computing the score of each question and the total score of the test using Spearman's correlation coefficient to check the validity of the test. Results of this statistical technique are stated in table (1) below.

Table 1: Spearman's Correlation Coefficient between each Question and Total Score

	Spearman's Correlation	p-value	#	Spearman's Correlation	p-value
1	0.43	0.049*	11	0.82	0.001**
2	0.49	0.029*	12	0.53	0.017*
3	0.52	0.019*	13	0.80	0.001**
4	0.44	0.049*	14	0.63	0.003*
5	0.64	0.002**	15	0.66	0.002**
6	0.52	0.019*	16	0.43	0.049*
7	0.53	0.017*	17	0.80	0.001**
8	0.80	0.001**	18	0.53	0.017*
9	0.80	0.001**	19	0.44	0.049*
10	0.44	0.049*	20	0.66	0.002**

** Statistically sig at 0.01 * statistically sig at 0.05.

The findings in table (1) show that all statements of the listening comprehension skills test are statistically significant at (0.01, 0.05) because all the correlation coefficient ranged between (0.43-0.82). The results indicate that the test is a valid tool and it suits the purpose of the study. An estimation of the listening comprehension test reliability over the pilot sample was predicated using Cronbach Alpha formula and it was (0.88) which proved its reliability.

Implementing the experiment of this study falls into the following steps:

- The researchers selected a set of videos from the internet websites like listen aminute.com and esl-lap.com. These websites offer simple access and samples of exercises.
- In addition, the researchers consider the diversity in the videos' topics among social, scientific, cultural and economic. The researchers designed a guide which helps them in implementing videos and the validity and reliability of this guide were ensured.
- The researchers explained the procedure of the listening sessions for English majors and their expected role during each procedure.
- The listening comprehension test was given to the sample of the study as pre-test.
- The participants of the study attended ten listening comprehension sessions in which they were motivated to watch translated English videos and answer a series of questions.
- The researchers displayed three videos in each session in which every video was repeated three times. The first and the third were displayed without translation and the second was displayed with translation.
- The listening comprehension test was given to the sample of the study as post-test.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 First Hypothesis

There are statistically significant differences at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) in the level of English majors' listening comprehension skills in the pre and posttest.

The researchers compared the scores of the participants of the study in the pre and post listening comprehension tests using Wilcoxon Test. Results of this test is state in Table 3.

Table 3: The Result of Wilcoxon Test

Listening Comprehension Skills		Mean	St. D	Relative Weight %	Mean Diff	Z- test	Sig
Listening Comprehension Skills	Pre	32.5	9.4	54.2	-15.70	-3.92	0.001**
	Post	48.2	6.1	80.3			
Getting the Main Idea	Pre	9.2	4.3	46.0	-9.00	-3.84	0.001**
	Post	18.2	2.0	91.0			
Getting Details	Pre	10.4	5.7	52.0	-4.10	-2.98	0.003**
	Post	14.5	3.5	72.5			
Note Taking	Pre	12.9	4.6	64.5	- 2.60	-2.40	0.016*
	Post	15.5	4.6	77.5			

** Statistically sig at 0.01 * statistically sig at 0.05

The results in the Table 3 above show that there are statistically significant differences between the pre and post mean scores of the listening comprehension skills test ($Z = -3.92$, $p\text{-value} = 0.001$) among English majors at AUG. The mean scores of the post test of listening skills equals (48.2), but in the pretest equals (32.5), which indicates that using

translated English videos has a role in enriching the listening skills among English majors.

The results show that there are statistically significant differences between the pre and posttest mean scores in getting the main idea skill ($Z = -3.84$, $p\text{-value} = 0.001$) among English majors. The mean scores of the participants of the study in getting the main idea of the posttest equals (18.2) whereas the pretest equals (9.2). Besides, there are statistically significant differences between the pre and posttest mean scores in getting details skill ($Z = -2.98$, $p\text{-value} = 0.003$) among English majors. The differences are in favor of the posttest. The mean score of the posttest in getting details skill equals (14.5), meanwhile in the pretest equals (10.4), which indicates that the use of translated English videos is a very important on enhancing getting details. The results also show there are statistically significant differences between the pre and posttest mean scores in note taking skill ($Z = -2.40$, $p\text{-value} = 0.016$) in favor of the posttest. The mean score of the posttest in note taking skill is (15.5) while that of the pretest is (12.9). This clearly shows that the use of the translated English videos has a very great role on enhancing the note taking skills.

B. Second Hypothesis

To identify the effect level of translated English videos on enhancing the AUG English majors' listening comprehension skills, the researchers used the Cohen's coefficient and eta square.

The results are illustrated in Table 4:

Table 4: The Effect Size of Translated Videos

Skills	Eta	D	Effect size
Listening Comprehension Skills	0.63	2.61	Big
Getting the Main idea Skill	0.44	1.76	Medium
Getting details Skill	0.50	1.98	Big
Note taking Skill	0.39	1.60	Medium

The data analysis in the above table (4) shows that the effect size is (0.63). The three listening skills are affected by translated English videos in different degrees. For example, getting details skill ranked first (0.50), while getting the main idea skill ranked in the second position (0.44). The skill of note taking ranked third one (0.39) which is considered the least skill affected by translated English videos.

Results show that translated videos have a big positive effect on enhancing listening comprehension skills. This result is in agreement with a number of studies which were conducted around the world. For instance, Gorjian (2014) showed that translated video has a great effect on enhancing vocabulary recognition. Also, Rokni & Ataee (2014) concluded that watching movies with subtitles has positive effect compared with effect of watching movies without subtitles on improving listening comprehension skills. In addition, Gowhary et al (2015) showed the positive effects of the video captioning on Iranian EFL learners. The researchers attributed the success of translated English videos on enhancing AUG English majors' listening skills to a number of factors.

Considering English majors' language level and interests in the presented videos grasp their attention and motivation. Selecting several types of videos and organizing several types of activities attracts English majors' attentions and concentration and meets individual differences. Furthermore, translated videos created enjoyable social and interesting atmosphere. Such atmosphere generates English majors' desire towards enhancing their listening comprehension and facilities achieving the aims of each listening session. In addition, listening and seeing the speakers at the same time stimulates multiple senses (Hosogoshi, 2016, p.155). Such audiovisual material activates senses and contributes in helping English majors completing activities correctly. The translated English videos served the function of visualizing and facilitating the meaning which leads to enhancing English majors' attitudes towards the use of translated English videos in learning listening. This proves the fact, that several scientific researches revealed, which says that the information acquired by joining and connection between more than one sense stays in the long-term memory.

Inserting the mother tongue in the process of teaching the foreign language may facilitate the content and make it easier in which Arabic facilitates the complex foreign meaning. The presence of translation also makes learning from audio-visual materials easier. Moreover, subtitles may help English majors to check their understanding of listening material and "*provide additional confirmatory/ non confirmatory evidence of what was comprehended*" (Winke, Gass and Sydorenko, 2010, p. 81).

Following well-organized steps for using translated English videos during the listening sessions and replaying the video three times may enable English majors to pick up the target and acquire mastery of listening skills. Further, replaying video several times may leading to deep understanding of the video idea. In the first listening they may get the general idea of the video easily. While in the second listening they may able to answer questions about details. And in the third listening they can take notes easily.

5. Recommendations

In the light of the results viewed throughout this study, the researchers find it is important to give some recommendations for English majors and for the teachers to develop listening proficiency. The English majors need to extensively practice listening in their daily activities by listening to several materials to enhance their listening skills. Besides, they have to expand their ability of listening by watching translated films and videos. The teachers have to find suitable strategies and learning tools to overcome the challenges and the difficulties of listening among English majors by adopting modern techniques such as translated English videos. It is necessary to consider individual differences and increase positive feelings and attitudes towards listening comprehension skills as they are not receptive skills otherwise, they are interactive skills. It is important to expose students to the natural use of English with native speakers, so that they can observe and acquire the listening skills. Finally, the researchers recommend conducting

studies on the effect of translated English videos on enhancing the skill of speaking and vocabulary recognition of English majors.

6. Pedagogical Implications

It is worth for English teachers/instructors to consider the following implications during listening sessions:

- 1) Raise the awareness of English majors towards the importance of watching translated English videos using different types of videos that attracts their interest and attention and meet learning styles. Besides, guides them to use the related websites.
- 2) Be more tolerant with English majors' errors to decrease their anxiety.
- 3) Be active and encourage English majors for more training courses and always give additional websites for teaching listening and guide English majors to many different sources.
- 4) Provide English majors with various resources of English listening materials that enhance their autonomy in learning the target language.
- 5) Use translated English videos in listening classes and evaluate students' achievement regularly.

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Sumer Salman Abou Shaaban earned a PhD in curriculum and teaching methods in 2009 from Ain Shams University, Egypt, and is now an associate professor in the Curriculum and Teaching Methods Department of the Faculty of Education, Al-Azhar University-Gaza, and since 2014 has served as the Deputy Dean of Planning and Quality Assurance Affairs. Sumer supervises and acts as an internal examiner for students completing their M.Ed. theses at AUG. She has published a number of papers in local and international journals and conference proceedings, and often serves as a reviewer for papers submitted to local journals and conferences. She is a certified PCELT master trainer.

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